

Flow Analysis of Gigabit Computer Network traffic at wireshed using Monosek

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Abstract—Flow Analysis, instead of just packet analysis has become a critical requirement in current scenario of connected world. But with gigabit networks being a reality, software solutions at identifying of flows that each network packet belongs to, can be time and resource consuming, thereby defeating the very purpose of flow detection requirement. In this paper, we show how using the hardware Flow-ID feature of Monosek network analysis engine, we can quickly and easily segregate packets into flows for further flow analysis.

Keywords—Network layers, Protocol Analysis, Flow ID, Hashing, Deep packet inspection, Pattern match

I. INTRODUCTION

We live in a connected world, where privacy of sensitive data can be at stake. While commercially there are several Firewalls, UTMs and content aware routers/switches, there are very few tools that cater to development community, especially when it comes to deep packet inspection, which includes payload. Complexity arises when we need to do flow inspection, wherein we have to check for a pattern in payloads across packets of a flow. This is where we need to identify which flow each packet belongs to. Monosek is a specialized hardware that caters to this requirement. We will use one of many specialized features of Monosek, viz Flow ID and apply it for a few interesting applications, quickly, easily and correctly.

II. NEED FOR FLOW ANALYSIS

First of all, we need to understand the importance of flow analysis. Traditionally, computer network analyzers have depended on header analysis or even payload analysis on a per-packet basis, i.e. each packet is analyzed independent of its previous or next packet characteristics. This would work well, as long the analysis is limited to a few statistics requirements, such as bandwidth, number of hits to a server, server response to total number of requests and such statistics. This served well in the early days for several applications and scenarios. But as internet became more consumer oriented and world became connected, then came the threat of network attacks becoming a global threat. Even here, in the initial days, packet header and payload would provide enough information to check if the packet is malicious. But as network hacks started becoming

more sophisticated and complex, there was a need to examine the payloads across several consecutive packets of a flow. This assumed critical dimension with internet speeds increasing to gigabit and beyond. With intelligence becoming part of networks, content aware routers and switches, next-gen firewalls and sophisticated firewall applications require flow analysis rather than just packet analysis. The content we are looking for may have spread across packets of the flow. Once we identify that packets of a flow are malicious, it is important to take action on the entire flow – for example to stop the flow into the network. This requires that we identify each flow and flow ID to which each packet belongs to. Another important need to flow analysis is for traffic forwarding. Based on flow, you may want to forward to flow to one of the ports or drop the flow or send it to host for analysis. In this case also we need flow analysis, rather than just packet analysis. An interesting application using Flow ID will be to recreate an entire session. By simply looking at flow ID, we can segregate the flows and then assemble payloads of all packets belonging to a flow to re-create the entire session. This would greatly help admin to monitor web activities by users of a campus network or of a corporate network.

III. FLOW ANALYSIS IN SOFTWARE

Flows are uniquely identified by a set of header fields. Assuming flows use either TCP or UDP protocols at the Datagram layer, we can safely conclude that the following 5 tuples will determine unique flows.

1. Source IP address
2. Source Port number
3. Destination IP address
4. Destination Port number
5. IP protocol – UDP or TCP

There can be several ways to generate flow ID. One way is simple and straight forward, as shown in figure 1.

Here, a flow ID is generated by comparing 5-tuples of each packet and for each unique combination of these fields a new flow ID is generated, and the packet is assigned the

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corresponding flow ID. If a packet has same combination of the 5 tuples as any of the previous packets for which a Flow ID is already generated, then this packet is assigned the corresponding Flow ID.

thereby will not achieve our goal of packet forwarding or session creation in real-time at wire-speeds.

IV. FLOW ANALYSIS IN MONOSEK

Monosek being a specialized hardware, computes the flow ID in hardware, thereby completely transforms flow analysis. The complexity of creating a flow ID is totally offloaded into the hardware and we can focus on usage of flow ID rather than dealing with complexities of creating one.

Figure 2 shows blocks inside a network flow engine card.

Figure 1: Flow chart for Flow ID Generation

This approach has several advantages. Being simple, it is easy to understand and implement in software. It also guarantees a new flow ID for upto 2^{31} (4 Gig) unique combination of the 5 tuples. But it also has a few disadvantages. One is to have a table with each row having all 5 tuple entries, thereby each entry occupying as many as 14 bytes (4+2+4+2+2). Also, comparison must happen for each of these 5 fields for each row. Even if we assume the table has just about 500000 entries (corresponding to flows), we are talking about one million comparisons in the worst case. To overcome this, many papers have suggested using hashing techniques. Here, a fast hashing algorithm creates a 4 byte hash value for the whole 14-byte field. This will reduce space in each row to just 4 bytes instead of 14 bytes. It also reduces 5 comparisons to a single comparison. So, if the hashing algorithm is fast enough, then the overhead of computing hash value can greatly be offset in the storage space and comparison time savings.

In either of these two approaches, the main issue is the computational overhead. If this computational time exceeds incoming packet arrival time, then we will start losing packets,

Figure 2: Network Flow Engine Blocks

As we can see, there are dedicated hardware blocks that operate parallelly to ensure no latency while computing flow ID. The card can maintain 6 million concurrent flows with unique flow ID for each flow. The card itself uses the flow ID to determine what to do for packets for each flow – like drop, forward to another port or send the packet to host. It also can send TCP packet with RESET TCP flag set, to the originating host, so that if required, connection with offending website can be terminated. Flow IDs are sequentially incrementing numbers for each new flow in Monosek. If the flow ID is generated in software using hashing technique, it will be the hash value of the 5-tuples. The flow ID will be same for all packets belonging to the flow.

Using this flow processing at wire-speed capability of Monosek, we can do flow analysis in real-time. We can also do session re-creation at almost real-time. This also reduces storage overhead. Thus, Monosek can be ideally used for flow analysis without sacrificing wire-speed analysis requirements. For flow analysis, we have created the following setup.

The following can be achieved because of flow ID feature of Monosek

1. Virus signature or Malicious content matching across packets of a flow: In absence of a hardware assisted flow ID generation, it is practically impossible to carry out pattern matching at wire-speed for patterns that may span across two or more consecutive packets. But

a hardware assisted flow ID generation can be used to identify packets belonging to same flow without any software overhead. This saves computational overhead,

Figure 3: Monosek Setup for Flow ID based analysis

increases search performance and guarantees detection of pattern even in boundary cases.

2. Session re-creation: This is a straightforward application if we have flow ID. All an application has to do is to segregate packets belonging to each flow and then reassemble the payloads of all the packets belonging to the particular flow, thereby recreating the session. Since Monosek provides a hardware assisted Flow ID for each packet, we can group all packets belonging to each flow at almost real-time, as we do not need to compute it in software. The details of how a flow ID needs to be generated in software is already covered in previous section.

In figure 4, we have shown a re-created email session. Of-course the explanation given above over-simplifies the actual process. In real world, we have to deal with several issues. To begin with, it will be timeouts. What if, due to network issue or server going down, a session stops abruptly in between? To take care of this in software, we have to build a state machine that goes through TCP states to confirm that every session in progress are active and not dead. However, Monosek provides a hardware assisted timeout feature, wherein it informs the host that a flow has outlived its expected life. This helps us to close the flowID and re-create the session. And then, there are possibilities of packets arriving out of order at the destination because of internet architecture. This means, if a packet arrives ahead of its actual position, we must wait till the previous packets arrive and then use this packet. Here again, sequence and acknowledge numbers of TCP layer is used by Monosek to identify if the packet is out of order.

Figure 4: Session Re-creation using Flow ID

In figure 4, we have shown a recreated email.

3. Application detection: This is an interesting feature that uses flow ID. Traditionally, using a simple firewall application, we could easily block an IP address, website name or a URL, for example an offensive website or one that is carrying out illegal activities or having malicious contents. But this is effective only if the user uses respective IP address or website name or URL. With advent of many bypass techniques these days, they may use an app or through other indirect means to access the blocked website. Since the IP address or Website name or URL is not directly entered by the user, there is a possibility that the firewall may not block. Instead, if we can identify unique traffic pattern of each of such websites, then we can block a website even if the IP address or website name or URL are not directly entered by the user. This is where flow ID can be very effectively used. By analyzing the consecutive packets of each flow, we can arrive at traffic pattern and match with pre-defined application traffic pattern. This will indicate if the user is using some application without directly entering the IP address or website name or URL.

In figure 5, we have shown identification of a few applications using application pattern patch rather than just website.

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Welcome to Monosek Protocol Analysis DPI based experiment to
display all network traffic
Detected application protocol name is flow based service detection using DPI technique
SERVER IP :
192.168.1.36

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Flow ID | Flow Type | Pack Num | Num | Tag | Time Stamp | Src IP | Dst IP | App Field
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4047 | New Flow | 238139 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:47 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Twitter
4048 | Existing Flow | 238132 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:47 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Twitter
4049 | Existing Flow | 238108 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:47 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Twitter
4050 | New Flow | 238179 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:53 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | YouTube
4051 | Existing Flow | 240202 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:56 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Amazon
4052 | New Flow | 240201 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:57 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Amazon
4053 | Existing Flow | 240212 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:57 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Amazon
4054 | Existing Flow | 242011 | 1 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:06:57 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 | Amazon
4055 | New Flow | 257001 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:07:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4056 | Existing Flow | 257001 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:07:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4057 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4058 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4059 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4060 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4061 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4062 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4063 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4064 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4065 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
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4179 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4180 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4181 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4182 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4183 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4184 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4185 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4186 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4187 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4188 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4189 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4190 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4191 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4192 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4193 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4194 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4195 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4196 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4197 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4198 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4199 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4200 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4201 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4202 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4203 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4204 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4205 | Existing Flow | 257008 | 0 |  | Wed Jul 22 17:08:01 2020 | 192.168.1.36 | 192.168.1.1 |
4206 |
```

For this application, we have used Flow ID to collect first few packets of each flow, compare the flow pattern with well know application flow pattern and arrive at a decision as to which flow belongs to which application. As seen in the above screen shot, we have identified Amazon, twitter, You-Tube and other applications.

V. CONCLUSION

We have shown in this paper results of our experiments which show a few of interesting fields that flow analysis can be applied to. This was possible within practical constraints because of Hardware Flow ID feature of Monosek. We can extend this to further research, by connecting Monosek features to Machine learning techniques to create Virus signatures and pattern matches

REFERENCES

1. Real-Time Network Flow Identification System Z. Baruch, A. Peculea, M. Suci, Z. Majo Technical University of Cluj-Napoca Computer Science Department 26-28 Gh. Baritiu St., 400027 Cluj-Napoca, Romania
<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/68fc/8b4cdac92a0275ee4464b08953ad320ea282.pdf>
2. Traffic Analysis for Network Security: Two Approaches for Going Beyond Network Flow Data - Tim Shimeall
https://insights.sei.cmu.edu/sei_blog/2016/09/traffic-analysis-for-network-security-two-approaches-for-going-beyond-network-flow-data.html
3. What is a Network Traffic Flow? - Matt Hayes
<https://mattjhayes.com/2018/09/26/what-is-a-network-traffic-flow/>
4. Hash-Based Techniques for High-Speed Packet Processing Adam Kirsch, Michael Mitzenmacher, and George Varghese
<https://www.eecs.harvard.edu/~michaelm/postscripts/dimacs-chapter-08.pdf>
5. Deep packet inspection using Cuckoo filter - Mohammad Al-hisnawi ; Mahmood Ahmadi
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7976111>
6. An Active DDoS Defense Model Based on Packet Marking - Yongping Zhang ; Zhuqing Wan ; Mingming Wu
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5403249>
7. Comparison of Internet Traffic Identification on Machine Learning Methods - Lingjing Kong ; Guowei Huang ; Keke Wu ; Qi Tang ; Suying Ye
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8546682>